

The programme of the international symposium „The Mediterranean Pattern and the Extended Region of the Black Sea”

No	Day	Time	Activity	Place	Supervisers
1	Wednesday, 06.06.2012	12,00 – 19,30	Guests' arrival and transportation	Henri Coandă Airport – RIN Central Hotel	Marin Drămnescu, Eugen Lungu, Andreea Zamfira
2		20,00 – 21,30	Cocktail party	UESEL	Ragip Gokcel, Sorin Mitulescu, Ion Boboc

No	Day	Time	Activity	Place	Author	Title of the paper	Moderator / Chairman / Supervisor
1	Thursday, 07.06.2012	10,00 - 10,30	Official opening of the international symposium	Aula Magna UESEL	Fatih Gursoy, President of Lumina Educational Institutions Foundation	Opening address	Associate professor Filip Stanciu, Rector of UESEL
2		10,30 - 12,00	Inaugural conference		Professor Luigi di Comite, Ph.D., Aldo Moro University, Bari	„Demographic Structure and Migrations in the Mediterranean Basin”	
3			Inaugural conference		Professor Daniel Barbu, Ph.D., University of Bucharest	"The Transformations of Democracy in Southern and Eastern Europe"	
4			Inaugural conference		Professor Giovanni Lobrano Ph.D., University of Sassari	„Subsidiarity in Roman Law”	
5		12,00 – 12,30	Coffee break				Lecturer Marin Drămnescu, Ph.D.
		12,30 – 14,00	Session 1. Institutions and politics E 145				
6			Professor Gheorghe Stoica, Ph.D., UESEL, Bucharest			„Civil Society in Central and Eastern Europe”	Professor Daniel Barbu, Ph.D.
7			Lecturer Răzvan Pantelimon, Ph.D., Ovidius University, Constanța			„Populists and Populisms in Southern and Eastern Europe”	
8			Lecturer Marcela Monica Stoica, Ph.D. candidate, Dimitrie Cantemir Christian University, Bucharest			„Political Parties and European Elections. The Case of Romania”	
9			Lecturer Florin Mitrea, Ph.D., UESEL, Bucharest			„Balcanity and Balcanism. Imagological Discourses and Political Projects between East and West”	
10			Catalin Raiu, Ph.D. candidate, University of Bucharest			„The Bishop Bartolomeu Stanescu: A Christian-Democratic Attempt”	
11		14,00 – 15,00	Lunch break UESEL Restaurant				

		15,00 – 16,30	Session 2. Institutions and politics E 145				
12			Professor Adrian Pop, Ph.D., UESEL, Bucharest			„Regional Cooperation in the Black Sea Region between Desiderata and Accomplishments”	Professor Maurizio Vernassa Ph.D.
13			Lecturer Victor Negrescu, Ph.D., UESEL, Bucharest			„Development Assistance Policies in the Black Sea Region”	
14			Anamaria Elena Gheorghe, Ph.D. candidate, University of Bucharest			„The Wider Black Sea Region: Europe’s Gateway to Central Asia’s Resources”	
15			Lecturer Ionuț Cojocaru, Ph.D.,			„The Straits, a Geo-strategic Debate in the Great Powers’	

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			UESEL, Bucharest	Equilibrium”		
16			Lecturer Havvanur Şahin, Karaelmas University, Turkey	„Within the Context of International Relations, the 200th Anniversary of the Bucharest Treaty”		
17		16,30 – 17,00	Coffee break			
18		17,00 – 17,30	Workshop conclusions (1)		Professor Daniel Barbu, Ph.D., Professor Maurizio Vernassa Ph.D.	
19	Friday, 08.06.2012	10,00 – 11,30	Session 3. Institutions and politics E 145			
20			Associate professor Ion Boboc, Ph.D., UESEL, Bucharest	„Ideological Europeanization of Southeastern European Parties (1945-2012)”	Professor Collina Vittore, Ph.D.	
21			Associate professor Sorin Mitulescu, Ph.D., UESEL, Bucharest	„The European Integration of Mediterranean Countries, a Possible Model for Romania?”		
22			Lecturer Eugen Lungu, Ph.D. candidate, UESEL, Bucharest	„Realistic Perspectives on Military Security in the Black Sea Region during the New Putin Era”		
23			Professor Leonida Moise, Ph.D., Hyperion University, Bucharest	„Place and Role of State and Non-state Actors in Contemporary International Relations”		
24		12,00 14,00 –	Lunch break UESEL Restaurant			
		14,00- 15,30	Session 4. Institutions and politics E 145		Professor Gh. Stoica, Ph.D.	
25			Associate professor Adrian Basarabă, Ph.D., West University of Timișoara	„Migratory Flows Shaping Turkey during 1923-2010”		
26			Lecturer Gelu Sabău, Ph.D., "Hyperion" University, Bucharest	„Democracy Versus Nationalism. The A. C. Popovici Case”		
27			Researcher Maria Costea, Ph.D., Socio-Human Research Institute „Gheorghe Șincai” of the Romanian Academy, Târgu Mureș	„Brussels’ Diplomacy and the Romanian-Soviet Relations in 1939”		
28			Associate professor Simion Costea, Ph.D., „Petru Maior” University, Târgu Mureș	„Highlights of Romania’s Relations with Brussels, Reflected in Belgian Diplomatic Documents” „Brussels’ Diplomacy and the Romanian-Soviet Relations in 1939”		
28		15,30 – 16,00	Workshop conclusions (2)		Professor Collina Vittore, Ph.D., Professor Gheorghe Stoica, Ph.D.	
30		16,00- 16,30	Coffee break			
31		16,30-	Plenary session. Final conclusions		Associate professor F.	

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		17,30	Aula magna	Stanciu, Ph.D., Professor D. Barbu, Ph.D., Professor M. Migliorini, Ph.D., Associate professor D. Vasile, Ph.D., Professor C. Vittore, Ph.D., Associate professor S. Mitulescu, Ph.D., Professor S. Bayraktaroglu, Ph.D.	
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